

Experimental Analysis on the Growth and Development of Guava fruit fly (*Bactrocera Correcta Bezzi*) in Guava Varieties

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Abstract :

Guava (Psidium guajava L.) is an important fruit crop. It is also called as apple of tropics and poor man's apple. It is cultivated in many tropical and sub tropical regions. India is the largest producer of guava fruit followed by Pakistan, Mexico and Brazil. Guava crop is infested by several insect pests. Guava fruit fly Bactrocera Correcta (Bezzi) is widely spread in India, Sri Lanka and Pakistan. It is also found in Nepal, Myanmar, Thailand and China. It is commonly known as guava fruit fly. Its size is approximately 5.4 mm in length. During the observation on the period of growth and development of guava fruit fly, it was found that incubation period was minimum 1.90 days in Red Flesh variety and maximum 3.50 days in Allahabad Safeda. Larval period shows a range of variation from 8.30 to 11.75 days in Allahabad Safeda to Red Flesh variety, respectively. Pupal period was found maximum 13.00 days in Lucknow-49.

Keywords : Fruit fly, Incubation, Growth.

Introduction :

Guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) can be grown successfully in a variety of soil and climatic conditions (Arora et al; 2000). It grows well in a PH which may be

ranging upto 9.5 in various soils. Guava gives two crops in a year, one is rainy season crop known as “Mrig Bahar” and another is winter season crop “Amba Bahar”. Over 150 arthropod species used to attack fruit trees and cause serious damage and economic loss (Aluja 1986). Insect pests cause damage to guava crop by several types (Atwal and Singh, 1990). It includes losses in plant growth, flowering, fruit setting, fruit growth and development (Drew, 1988 and Jalaluddin et al; 2001). Guava crop has a good scope for farmers to increase their income. Recorded hosts include common guava (*Psidium guajava* L.), Mango (*Mangifera indica*), Peach (*Prunus persica*), Rose-apple (*Syzygium jambos*), citrus, ber (Steck, 2002 a). Guava contains a large number of antioxidants and Phytochemicals (Drew and Henecock, 1994). It contains a higher content of vitamin C and vitamin A and is a good source of pectin which is an important dietary fiber, fructose sugar; skin of fruit contains ascorbic acid in very high amount (Galli and Rampazzo, 2000). Crushed leaves are applied on wounds, ulcers, chewed to relieve toothache.

Material and Methods :

The investigation undertaken on the five varieties of guava that is Allahabad Safeda, Lucknow-49, Apple Colour, Red Flesh and Local Seedling. The experiment carried out at River bed area of Bithoor, Kanpur. The texture of experimental soil was sandy loam, well drained and medium fertility. The larvae of insects were reared on the fruits and plants of different varieties of guava crop.

Experimental Findings :

Data of the growth and development of the larval and pupal period have been presented in the Table-1 it is also known as guava fruit fly. It is brightly coloured little fly. Predominantly black with lateral stripes. It is found that incubation period was minimum 1.90 days in Red Flesh variety and maximum 3.50 days in Allahabad Safeda. It revealed statistically different results. Larval period showed a range of variation from 8.30 to 11.75 days in Allahabad Safeda to Red Flesh variety, respectively. Pupal period was found maximum 13.00 days in Lucknow-49. Total life cycle was completed in 20.95 to 26.15 days in Red Flesh variety of Lucknow-49, respectively.

Results and Discussion :

This species of fruit fly is widely distributed. It attacks on many hosts trees. Its increased incidence has been reported on guava and mango (Jalaluddin et al. 2004). The egg development completes in two days but depends upon the prevailing temperature. Its life span completed in 20.95 to 26.15 days in Red Flesh variety to Lucknow-49 (Mepheron and Steck 1996), (Dhiman and Batra 1998) and (Diaz-Fleischer et al. 2000) also observed similar results in their experiments.

**Table 1 : Period of growth and development of guava fruit fly
(*Bactrocera correcta* Bezzi)**

Sl. No.	Crop	Egg Incubation	Larval Period	Pupal Period	Total Period of Life Cycle
1.	Allahabad Safeda	3.50 (1.87)	8.30 (2.88)	12.00 (3.46)	23.8 (4.88)
2.	Lucknow-49	3.75 (1.94)	9.40 (3.07)	13.00 (3.61)	26.15 (5.11)
3.	Apple Colour	2.85 (1.69)	10.35 (3.22)	8.65 (2.94)	21.85 (4.67)
4.	Red Flesh	1.90 (1.38)	11.75 (3.43)	7.30 (2.70)	20.95 (4.58)
5.	Local Seedling	2.30 (1.52)	10.00 (3.16)	12.50 (3.54)	24.8 (4.98)
	S.E.±	0.65	0.116	0.080	0.117
	C.D. at 5%	0.15	0.260	0.062	0.262

Note : *Figures in parenthesis are transformed values.*

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